

REACTION OF HYPONITRATES WITH BENZOIC ACID IN MELT

Temperature of experiments : 150°C Time of duration : 20 minutes. Weight of benzoic acid taken : 0.246±0.002 g.

	TABLE 'A' (Sodium hyponitrate, Na ₂ N ₂ O ₃)				TABLE 'B' (Lithium hyponitrate, Li ₂ N ₂ O ₃)			
1. Weight of hyponitrate taken (g)	0.120	0.0604	0.0332	0.0212	0.090	0.0424	0.0206	0.0098
2. Nitrogen equivalent of hyponitrate taken (g)	0.0275	0.0138	0.00762	0.00486	0.02836	0.01322	0.006424	0.003855
3. Nitrogen equivalent of the nitrite formed in the solid residue	0.01372	0.00315	0.00315	Nil	0.01575	0.00175	0.0052	0.0024
4. N ₂ O ₃ in alkali found	0.0038	Nil	Nil	Nil	0.0285	0.0285	Nil	Nil
5. NO formed at N.T.P. (ml)	15.2	11.0	5.0	5.00	4.1	2.6	0.9	0.5
6. N ₂ O formed at N.T.P. (ml)	1.7	1.2	0.6	0.9	0.3	0.2	0.1	—
7. N ₂ formed at N.T.P. (ml)	1.2	1.8	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.2	—	—
8. Nitrogen equivalent in the gas mixture found (g)	0.01433	0.01066	0.004553	0.004648	0.013678	0.012625	0.001230	0.00052
9. Total nitrogen found (g)	0.02665	0.01361	0.00703	0.004648	0.02867	0.01337	0.00648	0.003075

in one experiment with sodium hyponitrate. Its presence was found in appreciable amounts in the case of lithium hyponitrate. The results of the gas analysis indicate the presence of a large amount of nitric oxide and nitrogen. However, in the case of lithium hyponitrate the amounts of nitrous oxide and nitrogen displaced are much less.

The presence of three types of gases and quite appreciable amounts of nitrite in solid residue indicate that the reaction proceeds according to the following equations :

Nitrous oxide is formed by the decomposition of hyponitric acid according to the following equation :

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Chemical Investigation of the Trunk-Bark from *Ficus-Racemosa*

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IN the present communication the nature of chemical constituents present in ethanol extract of the trunk-bark of *Ficus-racemosa*, is discussed. A crystalline compound C₂₉H₅₀O, m.p. 135°-36°, has been isolated from ethanol extract of the bark (found : C, 84.09 ; H, 11.93%).

The compound was characterized as β-sitosterol by comparison of m.p. and IR spectrum with an authentic sample. It formed an acetate¹, m.p. 126° and a benzoate¹ m.p. 144°. It also gave a positive Salkowski-Hens reaction and developed a green colour in Burchard Liebermann test for sterols.

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